

Analysis of events relevant to parent bodies and the formation of Shahdad chondrites

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ABSTRACT

4 pieces of meteorites (KM97002, KM97003, KM97008, KM970010) which have been classified in previous studies and according to them, these meteorites are ordinary meteorites, chondrites with petrological type H₄. In this study, it is attempted that the events which are occurred in the asteroid parent body (Eros) of these fragments, which form evidence in the minerals (opaque minerals, kamacite, taenite) sulfide phase, matrix, CAIs, rings and rims, exist to be expressed in isolation. In this regard, first, after field studies and researches, as well as using microscopic polarization and reflection studies, we looked at the formation of metal elements and phases. In this way, it can be achieved to simulate the thermal evolution of the early asteroid Eros and can reconstruct the thermal history. Using this information is beneficial because of possibility identification more accurate analysis of the processes affecting the formation of the asteroid, and it will also be much easier to answer the question that whether it was formed before the asteroid formation, and the chondrites have been hit by interplanetary suspended projectiles.

Key words: Asteroid parent body, Opaque mineral, Matrix, CAIs, Asteroid thermal evolution.

1. INTRODUCTION

The origin of ordinary chondrites' parent bodies are not a mystery [1]. It is quite evident that these parent objects are somehow hidden in the S-type asteroids. Actually, most S-type asteroids are likely to be normal parent bodies of chondrites, because they exhibit the same spectral and mineralogical properties too [2] exactly like the chondrites of Shahdad, which belong to the Eros [3]. The level of almost all S-type asteroids (up to 200 km) have similar composition characteristics to those of high temperature meteorites (OC type 4 to 6) that interiors have been altered, and indicating this fact that collisions may have played an important role in the structural evolution of these asteroids [2][4]. Interestingly, according to some of the studies conducted by metallography, the cooling rate of H chondrites corresponded with these observations and showed that several initial bumps caused the body of the parent bodies of H chondrites to be dug in, while it was cooling down. It brings about disruption to the thermal history of many H chondrites and shows that several initial bumps are doged on H chondrites' parent bodies. It is disrupted the thermal history of many H chondrites, which eventually lead to the creation of surfaces containing rocks that are originated from a wide range of deep asteroid ingredients [5] [6] [7] [8].

2. Study methods

Initially, in order to collect related information on the relationships of chondrules and minerals, the processes and factors affecting the asteroid parent bodies, the book and related articles were studied. After the investigation, it began to identify minerals and chondrules (shape, type, abundance of chondrules), their relationship with each other, as well as the study of its optical properties in the microscopic studies of polarizing light and reflective light using the Zeiss research microscope in the laboratory of Kharazmi University of Tehran. To do this, we placed the samples in an ultrasonic bath for 2 hours to remove all ground effects (collision or exposure to the natural environment). The samples

were then placed in the oven at 110 degrees centigrade for drying about 48 hours. In the next step, imaging and density were done, and then a thin microscopic cross section was prepared for each sample and microscopic studies were conducted. In the case of identification matrix materials, CAIs, Fe- Ni and review of kamacite, troilite, taenite, copper elements, we studied them in reflective light and prepared polishing sections of them.

3. Microscopic studies of KM9700 chondrites

The mineral phases diagnosed in KM9700 are olivine and pyroxene. In this sample, olivine includes 26% and pyroxene 32% of the volume of meteorites, and these are the main mineral and often are euhedral- subhedral (Figure 1, 2). KM97002 sample includes chondrules that are related to the crystal and matrix sections, and in this accompaniment, pyroxene is surrounded by olivine, which indicates an temperature increasing in the asteroid parent bodies (Figure 3) [109]. In KM97003, the olivins around pyroxene have spinfex texture along the matrix of cryptocrystalline, and sometimes the chondrules of meteorites are formed with porphyry form of them (Figure 3). Some of these blade olivins are next to the spherical shape of the opaque, in which the iron and nickel alloys form are like that. It is seen, and some others are accompanied by the dominant texture of spherulite (Figure 3). The chondrules of this microscopic cross section in each centimeter are 2, which is composed of olivine spinfex or crystalline pyroxene or a combination of these two minerals (with an obvious boundary), it is sometimes specified and accompanied by 14% metal matrix. In some places, the microscopic sample of KM97008, barred olivine and occupies the succession of pyroxen and produces pseudomorph, while it has its own spinfex texture (Figure 4). Some olivins have spinfex texture, and due to the lack of opaque around this mineral, it is cryptocrystalin, and sometimes it is accompanied by a spherolith texture (Figure 5). In KM970010 chondrite, the volume of ordinary chondrule and compound chondrule in this sample is 80% and the chondrule of this cross section is perfectly fine boundary (5 chondrule in one centimeter) surrounded by a cryptocrystalin (Rim) with a size of 0.1 mm. In the context of the matrix, it is completely metal with an abundance of 11% (Figure 6). Compound chondrule with a diameter of 0.02 in this sample consists of olivine in chondrule with barred piroxen. Some granular olivins (GOs) that are located in the chondrules have spinfex, and in this type of olivins, the direction of each blade is not the same as the other blade, and each blade has differente oriented (Figure 6). Finally, it has been noted that these chondritic pieces are part of the H ordinary chondrite groups. The combination of silicate minerals and the boundaries of chondrules, which is well known, indicates that KM97002 belongs to petrology type 4 [10][3].

3.1 Microscopic studies of KM9700 chondrites (normal light)

For every centimetre of a microscopic sample, we have a chondrule, which is two types from a petrographic point of view. In some chondrules, mineral olivine is located in the center of the chondrule and is surrounded by mineral pyroxene, and in the others, pyroxen surrounds this part in the center and olivine (POP) (in some areas there is also a fusion of the radial texture of olivine and pyroxene (ROP)); while the main texture of pyroxene is barred (BP) with spinfex texture (filling particles of empty mineral space in this mineral tissue is opaque) next to the chondrule texture in the compound chondrule, it is located (Figure 1, 2). The main chondrules have a diameter of 0.5 mm. There are three chondrules in this form that have a certain boundary and fill a total of 60% of the sample level. In some places, it is easy to see the porphyritic olivine- pyroxene (POP) with a series of grains that are faded (Figure 3). They are 0.3 mm in diameter and have a volume of 68% some of them show normal porphyry texture that called POP (porphyry chondrule composed of olivine and pyroxene). The chondrules of this microscopic cross section in each centimeter are 2, which is made up of olivine spinfex or crystalline pyroxene or a combination of these two minerals that have a gradual boundary. It is sometimes known and is associated with 14% metal matrix. In others, the diameter of minerals that are part of meteorite slabs is 0.3 mm.

Most of the chondrules of this section are in the form of chondrule in the field of metal matrix with 12%. Chondrule in one centimeter and 65% filled the sample level. In this microscopic sample, chondrule is evident with a semi-specified boundary. Normal volume of chondrule and compound chondrule in this sample is 80% and the chondrule of this cross section is perfectly fine boundary (5 chondrule in one centimeter) surrounded by a halo of cryptocrystals (Rim) with a size of 0.1 mm. In the context of the matrix, it is completely metal with an abundance of 11% (Figure 6). Some granular olivins (GOs) that are located in the chondrules. They have a spinfex texture, and in this type of olivins, the direction of each blade is not the same as the other blade, and each blade has its own orientation (Figure 6). In some chondrules, parallel fractures are seen that recall the transformation of S_2 (Figure 6) [10][3].

Fig. 1. Sample KM97002. A chondrule with a perfectly fine boundary and closed radial texture of pyroxene and olivine (ROP) and the accumulation of cryptocrystalline particles that RIM have formed.

Fig. 2. KM97002 has barred pyroxene spinifex (BP) and an opaque mineral as a blade, plate fractures are evident in pyroxen

Fig. 3. Sample KM97003 has pyroxene in metallic matrix.

Fig. 4. The chondrule of KM97008 is filled with pyroxene.

Fig. 5. Sample KM97008. Pyroxene is inside the chondrule and has a spinifex texture, along with the chondrule and pyroxene, which are surrounded by olivine.

Fig. 6. Sample KM970010. Barred pyroxene (BP) in matrix field in normal light.

4. Microscopic studies of KM9700 chondrites (reflective light)

The study of opaque minerals is important because they record the thermal history of meteorites. The spherical metal phases present in some silicate minerals of Shahdad meteorites that are a factor in the formation of liquid droplets which come from an initial crystallized structure that have the same cooling rate of the Fe-Ni-S melting at 700 degrees and it resembles the textures found in the Tieschitz meteorite [11] [12]. Several sets in OCs are made up of Fe-Ni metal with troilite, while a large number of some Fe-Ni metal grains seen in polished parts appear to lack sulfide, most of these metals may actually be connected to the troilite in the third dimension at the base. On the other hand, many chromite grains appear to be monomineralic, while others are intertwined with kamacite or troilite. Approximately 1 percent of chondrules exhibit concave indentations on their surfaces, often referred to as cavities. Some of them are partially filled with opaque phases, usually metal and troilite, which appear to have been ejected due to centrifugal force while the chondrules were rotating and partially molten, resulting in the formation of these indentations during this event. troilite, kamacite and taenite are components of ordinary meteorites and are typically found in ferromagnesian silicates, in the matrix, and in metallic and sulfide aggregates (Figure 7). Opaque minerals constitute 20% of the KM9700 meteorite, which consists of troilite that have Fe, Ni grains, and the chromite, merrillite, pentlandite, and copper, which are in small amounts (Figure 7, a). Chromites are present in most areas of the microscopic sections and have a unique pattern of irregular arrangement with a size of 2-5 μm and are accumulated from other opaque phases or metals and troilites. Also, chromite is present in these meteorites as a small component (<0.3 micrometer) in chondrules and olivine crystals (Figure 8). Mafic silicates contain Fe, Ni (as inclusions) and small bowl-like fragments of chromites, similar to the chromite inclusions found in ordinary meteorites that have been reported after impact with the Earth. Kamacite can be observed in coarse-grained minerals (up to 1 mm in diameter) as well as in very fine mineral grains (0.1-0.5 μm), next to some chondrules and only in the matrix. Large minerals have very irregular margins, and some of them show typical H chondrite growth stages and maybe contain olivine inclusions or other things like natural copper. Tainite illustrates a lower tendency than kamacite to form smaller grains

in the assemblages of troilite, kamacite, and tetrataenite. Nickel-rich areas have been identified as transparent tainite (tetrataenite), which is surrounded by tainite with high Ni concentrations (wt% ± 50) that are concentrated at the edges, with some present in the center (wt% ± 30). Tetrataenite occurs as grains ranging from 5 to 50 micrometers, with some regions exhibiting rings of 1 to 20 micrometers on the tainite grains, and it is occasionally associated with troilite grains (Figure 7, b). In these chondrites (Shahdad meteorites), both kamacite and taenite are in an intergrowth and are responsible for the formation of the plessite phase [13] [9]. Troilite is slightly larger than other metal phases and can be seen approximately 1- 20 micrometer, and this is also the case with chromite. Sometimes polysomatic microscopic sections show rims of fine-grained olivine, pyroxene, and opaque phases in a glassy matrix. Taenite zone is a great interest because nickel profiles are useful for metallographic calculations of cooling agent rates [11]. Tetrataenite (which is formed by arrangement of Fe and Ni in taenite) creates rings around the taenite grains of chondrites at temperatures below 350°C and is a slow cooling factor [11]. The iron and nickel phases in these meteorites show a typical cooling process of a typical chondrite. Tetrataenite is obtained from iron and nickel at the border of kamacite and taenite zoning. In common chondrites, copper metal is less abundant than Fe-Ni metal alloy, this is present in several petrographic collections [17] [16] [15] [14] [11] (Figure 7, c). In the Shahdad meteorite, metallic copper with a size of 0.1-1.6 micrometers is either enclosed within Fe-Ni metal or is located in proximity to smaller troilite grains within the tainite. This type of irregular assembly is reported as the most common occurrence in normal chondrites and may have been caused by melting shock or local melting shock [14]. The effects of metamorphic shock on a metal assemblage such as meteorite troilite KM9700, based on the presence of flat fractures in olivine, irregular fractures and the presence of thin veins and opaque parts in the hand sample, are related to the S_2 metamorphic stage shock. Particles may also be associated with shock effects, and polycrystalline troilite, metallic copper, chromium, and Fe-Ni compounds in olivine are some of the other characteristics of this shocked chondrites [14] [11].

Fig. 7. Opaque minerals of Shahdad chondrites in reflective light. a) KM97002; very fine crystals of merrillite in olivine; spherical inclusions of Fe- Ni metals in olivine and pyroxene. b) Kamacite, next to olivine spinifex in KM97001; at the bottom of the image there is a taenite with poor internal reflection. c) KM97007 chondrite has copper spherical inclusions in kamacite next to the troilite. d) KM970019 with chromite inclusion in olivine.

Fig 8. Chromite particles.

4.1 Microscopic studies of KM9700's matrix section of chondrite

The fine-grain matrix in the OC consists mainly of $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ olivine grains ($Fa \sim 91$) and somewhat coarse grains of low- calcium pyroxene, albitic plagioclase. The metal is Fe-Ni (kamacite, taenite), troilite, chromite, merrillite, the ratio of which varies from chondrite to another chondrite (Figure 7, d). Chondrule fragments, isolated silicate particles and rare microchondrules are also present in the matrix. The cryptocrystalline matrix in Shahdad chondrites comprise 3% of the meteorite, in the opaque context, a metallic matrix with a volume of 10-14% is present, which is scattered on the surface of the microscopic sample. In these chondrites, the matrix part includes the accumulations of microcrystalline fragments that fill the space between the chondrules and the crystal parts, and the main part of the cryptocrystalline matrix is formed around the chondrules in the form of a ring (Fin grain Rim) [10] [3].

4.2 Other opaque mineral phase sections

Metal-sulfide and silicate melts do not mix completely in the asteroid parent bodies. When ordinary chondrites undergo impact melting, fine metallic grains tend to agglomerate and separate from the silicate melt. This process can lead to different outcomes: Metal and sulfide can solidify in the form of dispersed nodules up to centimeter size, as observed in the impact melt chondrite L- PAT 91501 [18], or in unique to the rapidly cooling chondritic molten rock (LAR 06299) LL [19], metal and sulfide droplets respond to the asteroid's gravitational field and align with gas bubbles (vesicles) (based on density, bubble at the top, troilite is melted in the middle and metallic iron is melted at the bottom).

5. Conclusions

In this study, after preparing thin and polished microscopic sections and studying them in polarized and reflective light, with previous investigations [10][3], fragments of this meteorite, which is a typical H₄ chondrite type, it belongs to the asteroid parent body of Eros, which according to the minerals evidence mentioned. The increase in heat, which can cause these two sources (two primary heat sources), which may have lead to metamorphic changing and meteorites melting:

- (1) Short-term radionuclide decay such as ²⁶Al (with a half-life of approximately 717,000 years).*
- (2) Heat from collision. It can be assumed that both mechanisms played an important role. For example, the collisions of asteroids that had previously been heated by the decay of ²⁶Al.*

Other proposed mechanisms of asteroid heating (such as thermogenic chemical reactions, adiabatic compression of nebula gas, explosive reconnection events in nebula, electromagnetic induction in primary solar wind) now have few supporters. In the thermal evolution of parent bodies, temperature reduction and cooling are also experienced. This is due to various factors, including evidence of sulfide phases resulting from metamorphic shock during impacts. Impacts from interplanetary projectiles, despite their small size, can generate a significant amount of molten material that becomes buried to considerable depths in the high-porosity asteroid parent body (typically of chondritic composition). This process leads to localized cooling, which can significantly influence the formation of mineralogical and geological structures within that body. Other evidence of temperature reduction can be referred to tetrataenite, which is also known as an important factor for slow cooling.

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